

Subjective Evaluation of Roughness for Perceptual Audio Coding

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Abstract— This study investigates correlations between roughness metrics (musical [1], acoustic [2]) and the perceived audio quality of CODEC compressed musical intervals. 16 samples were synthesised using 2 musical instruments, across 8 different note intervals and 4 audio conditions, which include uncompressed and 96kbps mp3 compressed audio and spectral manipulations of the harmonic content. Roughness metrics were extracted from the signals. 17 participants evaluated the BAQ of each sample using a MUSHRA listening test. A significant difference with a large effect size was found for audio conditions, whereas a significant but small effect size difference was found for musical intervals and instruments. Further, a correlation was found between perceived quality and roughness metrics, but the explained variance in the model was low.

large effect sizes for *Audio Conditions*. Anchor was judged significantly lower than all other conditions. A significant difference was also found in the EQ enhancements. (see Fig. 1) For the objective metrics of roughness and the BAQ scores, we found a negative correlation for musical roughness and a positive correlation for acoustic roughness. However, both are very weak with a variance explained below 4%(see result in Table. 2).

Figure 1. Boxplots of quality rating versus audio conditions collapsed across instruments and intervals of a figure caption.

I. INTRODUCTION

Perceptual audio coding (CODECs) is known to create artefacts in the coded signal. It is posited that the acoustic metrics of roughness are reasonable, objective, representations of these from a subjective standpoint [3]. A MUSHRA (Multiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor) based listening test was designed to draw a correlation between the subjective quality assessment and the roughness of audio samples.

II. METHOD

Two instruments, cello and pipe organ, playing the following note intervals, were synthesised: semitone, tritone, perfect-five, and minor seventh across two octaves, to produce various roughness levels created by the interaction of harmonic content. A digital equaliser was used to implement acoustic manipulation of the spectrum in each audio file. These were fundamental and 2nd harmonic enhancements of 10dB, for musical EQ, and fundamental and harmonic adjacent at 1kHz enhancement by 10dB, for acoustic EQ. Subsequently, samples were compressed using a LAME encoder to 96kbps mp3 format.

The listening test was conducted in an ITU listening room, using the WebMUSHRA[4] interface. Samples were reproduced from a laptop, via a pre-amp through Beyerdynamic DT990 PRO headphones. 17 participants took part in judging the basic audio quality (BAQ) of each sample.

III. RESULT

The data has 3 independent variables (intervals, instruments, audio conditions) and one dependent variable (BAQ). A 3-way rmANOVA (see result in Table. 1) with post-hoc paired comparisons found significant differences with

TABLE I. RESULT OF THREE-WAY RMANOVA

Effect Type	F	p	Effect size	Measure scale
Audio Conditions	31.907	.000	.421	Large
Intervals	2.467	.023	.008	Small
Instruments	5.903	.030	.004	Small
Audio Conditions × Intervals	2.139	.000	.035	Small
Audio Conditions × Instruments	20.481	.000	.073	Medium
Intervals × Instruments	0.949	.453	-	-
Audio Conditions × Instruments × Intervals	0.826	.774	-	-

TABLE II. CORRELATION OF AUDIO PERCEPTUAL RATING WITH THE ROUGHNESS VALUES (ACOUSTIC AND MUSICAL)

Factor	Acoustic roughness			Musical roughness		
	R	R ²	p	R	R ²	p
Audio Conditions	.084(-)	.007	.000	.190	.036	.000

IV. CONCLUSION

This study suggests that manipulations of spectral content are perceived as significant alterations of quality, which are independent of musical interval or instrumentation. Further, correlations between roughness metrics and perceptual quality were found to be weak, suggesting that perceptual quality might be more closely related to other signal metrics. Future studies will examine other timbral features (brightness, sharpness, etc.) for possible explanations.

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